

Extra-curricular Activities and Students' Character Development in Moroccan Higher Education: A Correlational Study

Ayman BELHIYAD

Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fès, Morocco

Abstract: *The present paper addresses the possibilities and the types of correlations between students' extracurricular experiences and their character development in the Moroccan higher education context. The sample of the study consisted of English department students from different Moroccan universities, including some students from Al Akhawayn University and other higher education institutions. To answer the main research question about whether there is a statistically significant relationship between extracurricular activities and students' morals, ethics, values and citizenship or not, mixed methods in data collection and analysis were employed. 220 students filled in the questionnaires and 17 students participated in three focus groups to study the correlation between extra-curricular activities and students' character and elicit their opinions and attitudes towards such correlations. Results from the questionnaires showed that there is a positive correlation between extra-curricular activities and students' character and character development. Focus groups results confirmed previous quantitative results and yielded interesting qualitative data as well. Overall, the research findings suggested that Moroccan policy makers, deans, faculty staff and teachers need not only to be aware of the importance of extra-curricular activities as well as the strong relationship these activities have with students' character but also create opportunities for students to engage in different extra-curricular opportunities aiming at developing their character, morals, ethics, values and citizenship.*

Key Words : Extra-curricular Activities, Character, Character Development, Ethics, Values, Morals, Citizenship

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the main reasons behind advocating character education in tertiary level is the fact that it is a reaction to the present university situation. Growing individualism and disinterest in the political and civic life have become prevalent among university students. During the last decades, colleges and universities have noticed that students pay less attention to offering help to others and more attention to gaining financial security. This is why a number of higher education institutions have responded by establishing leadership and character development programs, volunteer and community service centers as well as other programs designed to involve students as social participants in their institutions and community (Astin, 1993, Boyer, 1994, & Levine, 1994).

The Moroccan higher education has undergone many reforms since independence in 1956 to enhance the productivity of the educational system. However, these reforms have not taken students' character development into serious consideration. The Moroccan universities need a big step to help students develop their morals, ethics, values and citizenship. Furthermore, research into the development of students' character in Moroccan tertiary level is very limited, as most research is related to cognitive aspects and academic performance. One way to develop students' character is to engage in extracurricular activities which students benefit from while studying at university. Therefore, the aim of this study is to examine the correlation between extracurricular activities and students' morals, ethics, values and citizenship in the Moroccan university. It provides results, implication and recommendations to the teaching and administrative staff as well as stakeholders to make the university, especially via extracurricular activities, a place for character development for the good benefit of students and society at large.

2. REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

2.1 Morals and Morals Education

Morality could be seen as "having interpersonal behavior including rights, duties and welfare of either party." An action is moral "if it is consistent with what an actor independently judges to be morally right" (Candee & Kohlberg, 1987). Moral behavior is the combination of the individual understanding of morals, moral cognition, and a demonstration of behavior that fits social norms and moral standards. The features of moral behavior include an emphasis on altruism. The evaluation of moral behavior comes from the internal moral recognition and standards of an individual. It is also judged and reviewed from another perspective by the demonstration of social behavior, the evaluation of a long-term contribution to society (Finney, 2002).

Moral education is "concerned with enabling students to critically consider and revise their own commitments in a discursive process, with the help of, among other things, the scientific concepts of ethics, as a part of their reflective construction of their identity narratives" (Wardekker, 2004). In addition to the important roles of teachers in developing students' morality and values

within the classroom, the institution as a whole should "foster caring beyond the classroom", "create a positive moral culture in the school" and "recruit parents and the community as partners in character education" (Lickona, 1993).

2.2 Values and Values Development

Values are defined in the literature as standards for determining levels of goodness or desirability. The verb "to value" which means to prize, to esteem, to appraise and to estimate also refers to the act of cherishing something and holding it dear (Sindhvani & Kumar, 2013). As a matter of fact, though there is an agreement on the importance of values teaching and character training, there is little consent upon what values to teach. Teachers should teach values which enable young people to maximize their use of their education and knowledge (Brynildssen, 2002). Moreover, there are a number of important values to teach mainly respect and responsibility in addition to wisdom, justice, fortitude, self-control, love, positive attitude, hard work, integrity, gratitude, and humility (Lickona, 2004). Other crucial values include compassion, courtesy, honesty, fairness, loyalty, perseverance, and responsibility (Edgington, Brabham, and Frost, 1999).

The world today witnesses a new interest in values, a reemergence of values and character education in current higher education. There are many reasons behind integrating values education in the higher education (Dalton, 1985). One of the reasons behind the renewal of student affairs staff interest and involvement in values education is due to the prevalent concern about the absence of ethical values in college student. Besides, there has been a tendency of increasing materialism and hedonism in addition to a corresponding decline in altruism and social consciousness among college (Astin, 1977). Carnegie Foundation studies supported Astin's general assessment of contemporary college student values. Disillusionment with society's values and institutions as well as fear of the future have caused college students to become morally cynical and self-centered (Levine, 1980).

2.3 Ethics and Ethics Development

The English word 'ethics' is derived from the ancient Greek word *ēthikós*, meaning "relating to one's character", which itself comes from the root word 'ēthos' meaning "character, moral, nature". Then, the word 'Ethics' was borrowed into Latin as 'ethica' and then into French as 'éthique', from which it was borrowed into English (Farhud, 2019). Moreover, ethics implies both the existence of action and the existence of others, as it will manifest through a person's responsible and conscious acts, creating guidelines for human actions to follow (Battestin, Bergamo & Gazzola, 2016).

The process of developing an ethical framework (codes of ethics) in higher education should take 10 criteria into consideration. These criteria are "leadership and endorsement", "allocate time and resources", "build on existing ethics-related documents", "learn from others", "think about language and length", "decide on a beginning and an end", "chose a structure", "produce and test a first

draft” and “finalize the framework” (The Council for Industry and Higher Education, 2005).

2.4 Citizenship and Community Service

Definitions of citizenship can be classified into three types: *a narrow definition*, *a middle definition* and *a broader definition*. The broader definition of citizenship moves beyond the simple legal status of a citizen and his/her knowledge for participation in the political sphere to the board combination of the knowledge about society, the skills for effective participation in society and the dispositions to engage constructively in public efforts to promote the common good (Althof & Berkowitz, 2006). Moreover, three main aspects of citizenship are identified: *commitment to social activism*, *sense of empowerment* and *community involvement*. The first aspect refers to certain life goals and participating in community action programs as well as influencing social values and political structures while the second one refers to a person’s sense and feeling about his/her ability to bring changes in society. The last aspect refers to participation in voluntary work or community service (Sax, 2004).

Community service has positive effects on students’ character and moral development. Indeed, community service influences one’s moral reasoning and attitudes, development of the self, opportunity for action, personality, and social characteristics (Hart, Atkins & Donnelly, 2006). Community service affects students’ moral attitudes and facilitates their moral judgment development (Conrad & Hedin 1982). Furthermore, service learning students have higher levels of some aspects of social problem solving than non-service students (Batchelder & Root, 1994). Thanks to volunteering, students’ attitudes toward others, mainly those different from them, had changed for the better (Boss, 1994). Indeed, the reciprocal nature of service learning presents unique opportunities for moral growth (Brandenberger, 2005)

Morality and moral development are linked to experiential learning. Experiential and co-curricular involvement such as community outreach and leadership opportunities might play a key role in students’ moral (King and Mathew, 2002). Service learning participants showed significant positive differences compared to non-participants. College students who participated in service learning were more likely to be civically engaged after five years of graduation (Sax and Astin, 1997). Also, youth participation in community service contributes to moral development by generating interest in addressing community problems and increasing confidence in one’s ability to be an effective force of change (Youniss and Yates, 1997). Last but not least, service learning courses and programs yield significant moral change thanks to reflection, as students reflect on service activities and open discussions in which they share their various interpretations of the common experiences and discover the ways service activities affected their understanding of and their relationship with the people they worked with (Eyler & Giles, 1991).

3. METHOD

3.1 Research Problem

The purpose of this study was to examine the correlation of students’ character and students’ extracurricular experiences in Moroccan tertiary level. More specifically, the objective was to assess the correlation between extracurricular activities and students’ morals, ethics, values and citizenship. To address this issue the following research question was formulated:

Is there a statistically significant correlation between extracurricular activities and students’ morals, ethics, values and citizenship?

3.2 Setting and Participants

This study took place during the academic year 2018-2019. The participants were English department students from different Moroccan universities with the exception of some students from Al Akhawayn University and other higher education institutions. The majority of respondents were from Abdelmalek Essaâdi University, Tetouan (37.27%) and Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University, Fez (19.09%). The participants were from different educational levels: Undergraduate (86%), M.A. (10%) and PhD (4%). While the respondents who filled in the online questionnaire were basically accessible thanks to social networks, mainly Facebook, and direct personal contacts with some university students, respondents who participated in the focus group were students from *Abdelmalek Essaâdi University* in Tetouan and *Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University* in Fez.

3.3 Instruments and Procedures

To study this correlation, the researcher opted for mixing questionnaires and focus groups for triangulation. This research employed a self-administered questionnaire to study students’ character (morals, values, ethics and citizenship), extracurricular activities and the correlations among the underlying sub-variables. Besides, given the complex nature of students’ character and their extracurricular experiences, it would have been impossible to have a comprehensive and deep understanding of the variables under study as well as the relationship between the two variables based on recording students’ attitudes and opinions on Likert and Frequency Scales only. Thus, focus group is used as helping research instrument to obtain respondents’ views and opinions about the issue under study.

The strategy used in this study was non-probability sampling, particularly convenience sampling and volunteer sampling. In this study, 220 students responded to the questionnaire and three focus groups with 17 students were conducted on the 25th of March, the 1st and the 4th of April, 2019. It is important to mention that there were no incentives for requesting students’ participation in filling out the research questionnaire or participating in the focus group. The participants chose to get involved in this study voluntarily and were very helpful because they filled the online questionnaire in and sent it back quickly. Finally, to analyze data and answer the research question, Pearson’s’ correlation analysis and thematic analysis were used. Results from quantitative data were presented in tables while results from qualitative data were presented in the form of paragraphs.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Quantitative Data: Pearson’s Correlation Analysis

Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) was adopted. Moreover, Pearson’s correlation coefficient test was conducted to find out the correlation between students’ extra-curricular activities and students’ morals, values, ethics and citizenship and to test the null hypothesis:

H 0: There is no correlation between extra-curricular activities and students’ character.

Table 1

Pearson Correlations for Extra-curricular and Morals, Values, Ethics and Citizenship

Correlations		Extra-curricular activities	Morals	Values	Ethics	Citizenship
Extra-curricular Activities	Pearson Correlation	1	.307**	.213**	.423**	.516*
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000	.001	.000	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220
Morals	Pearson Correlation	.307**	1	.624**	.474**	.409*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220
Values	Pearson Correlation	.213**	.624**	1	.435**	.380*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.001	.000		.000	.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220
Ethics	Pearson Correlation	.423**	.474**	.435**	1	.540*
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	220	220	220	220	220
Citizenship	Pearson Correlation	.516**	.409**	.380**	.540**	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	220	220	220	220	220

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

A Pearson correlation analysis was employed to test the linear relationship between extracurricular activities and morals, values, ethics and citizenship.

The output in the table above revealed a weak positive relationship between *extra-curricular activities* and *values*, $r=.21$. The results also showed a moderate positive relationship between *extra-curricular activities* and *ethics*,

$r=.42$ as well as *extra-curricular activities* and *morals*, $r=.30$. The output also revealed that there is a strong positive relationship between *extra-curricular activities* and *citizenship*, $r=.51$. Besides, the results provided evidence that the correlation coefficient was statistically very significant, $p<.01$. On the basis of these results, it can be concluded when the students engage in extra-curricular activities aiming at developing their character, their morals, values, ethics and citizenship develop as well.

4.2 Qualitative Data: Focus Groups

4.2.1 Morals and Values

Most respondents believed that university students demonstrate high degree of *responsibility, respect, self-esteem, honesty* and *trustworthiness*. One respondent said:

You will develop your personality. You will develop all these values. You will try to be more responsible. You will try to be fairer with your classmates. You will be more passionate more respectful and you will give the opportunity to everybody to speak you can be honest.

However, some respondents disagreed about certain values like *trustworthiness, honesty, kindness* and *hard work*. According to them, not all students are *wise, trustworthy* or possess *positive attitudes*. One respondent said: “*There are some students who have good morals and there are some students who are honest and confident but there are other ones, I think, they don’t have good morals.*”

Some unexpected subthemes emerged in the focus group data are *acceptance, help, justice, maturity, care* and *being passionate*. *Acceptance*, a subtheme emerged many times by respondents, is a very important value which denotes accepting people as different personalities, being non-judgmental and accepting different opinions and worldviews.

Regarding values, respondents agreed that the most important values students have are *hard work, kindness* and *love*. Other values mentioned by respondents are *gratitude, humility* and *positive attitudes*.

4.2.2 Ethics

Most participants agreed that *accepting criticism, generosity, self-independence* and *willing to learn from failure* are the major ethics which university students possess. One respondent said:

Also, people (students) do not have a problem to give you [their notes] for example there are some students who work ... so we as students, we give them the courses and when these student come and ask for the handout or the notes, we are here to help...So we are just if you want like to say generous.

Other important values mentioned only once in the focus groups data are *self-discipline, positive attitudes* and *courage*. However, some respondents had different opinions about students’ ethics at university. They disagreed about *accepting criticism, discipline* and *willing from failure*. One respondent has a different viewpoint. She said:

There are some characters or some of the values you have mentioned we kind of feel like they are really rare ... like accepting criticism ...willing to learn

from failure...we find them like really rare in the university life.

Last but not least, three emerging subthemes that respondents mentioned in the discussions are *motivation*, *open-mindedness* and *acceptance*.

4.2.3 Citizenship

Most respondents had negative attitudes towards *civic behavior*, *civic skills*, *community service*, *voluntary work*, *citizenship* and *being a good citizen*. One respondent said:

Actually I found that the majority of university students, they don't care about these things. They don't care about voluntary work, about volunteering your time, giving your time for other people or sacrificing like your own energy and your own time for the benefit of others.

Respondents also had negative attitudes towards *political life* and *political activism* at university. According to them, political life and activism at university is a waste of time. Another respondent added:

For me, some students, they are having an idea about university is not about studying, it's about, you know, defending their survival and I'm here I'm talking about students political groups. When I came here I took a decision that I will study, I would go to my personal issues because I found that it's like I gave up on the state of being active, you know.

4.2.4 Extra-curricular activities

Most respondents mentioned that they lack extra-curricular activities such as *clubs*, *special programs*, *internship programs*, *vocational training* or *service learning opportunities*. When asked about these activities, some respondents kept silence and seemed disappointed. One respondent said: *"I think what is lacking in this institution here is clubs"*. Furthermore, respondents believe that extracurricular activities have a relationship with character development. When asked about the relationship between extracurricular activities and character development, a number of positive responses were given by respondents like: *"Yes of courses"*, *"Yes...It makes them confident."*, *"Yes for 100 per cent."* Besides, respondents believe that such activities have positive impact on students, as they help them in their studies and make them feel more confident and creative. One respondent said:

Yes, that will make you confident, confident and creative...it helps you, you know, be creative in your life and it makes you creative and if you are creative, people will find out and you will be convinced that you are creative.

5 DISCUSSION

The quantitative and qualitative data suggest interesting results regarding the correlation between college extra-curricular activities and students' character mainly their morals, ethics, values and citizenship. Exactly, Pearson's correlation test provided statistical evidence that university extra-curricular activities correlate positively with

their character and character development. On the basis of these results, it can be concluded that students believe that if they engage in extra-curricular activities at university and even outside the university milieu, their character will develop.

More significant, the qualitative results reveal that the majority of college students do not have extra-curricular activities such as clubs, special programs, vocational training and service learning opportunities with the exception of some music and sport activities, mainly playing soccer by males. Besides, approximately all respondents believe that extra-curricular activities have a positive impact on university students, helping them in their studies and making them feel more confident and creative.

It is important to mention that the quantitative and qualitative results yield different but complementary data concerning the correlation between extracurricular activities and students' morals, values, ethics and citizenship as shown above. One plausible explanation is that although the majority of respondents does not take part in extra-curricular activities for various reasons, they not only believe that there is a strong relationship between extra-curricular activities and character but also that such activities are crucial and have positive influence on their character and character development.

These findings support King and Mathew's (2002) research that experiential and co-curricular involvement such as community outreach and leadership opportunities play a key role in students' moral development. The findings also support Eyer & Giles' (1991) argument that service learning courses and programs have influential potentials on students' moral because they yield significant moral change due to reflection. As a matter of fact, thanks to service learning opportunities, students reflect on service activities and open discussions in which they not only share their various interpretations of the common experiences, but also discover the ways service activities affected their understanding of and their relationship with the people they worked with. Moreover, the research findings are in line with Brandenberger's (2005) argument that service learning, which is part of engaged pedagogies, enable students to test their developing moral thinking in a challenging environment they may otherwise avoid and to learn how to learn in moral domain. In addition, the research output support Sax and Astin's (1997) studies that the college experience and particularly engaged pedagogies, including service learning, foster moral development. Their studies demonstrate not only the fact that service participants show significant positive differences compared to non-participants but also that college students who participate in service learning are more likely to be civically engaged after college graduation. Furthermore, the research findings are in agreement with Youniss and Yates' (1997) confirmation that community service participation contributes to students' moral and character development. It also generates interest in addressing community problems and increasing confidence in students' ability to be an effective force of change. Additionally, the research output supports Conrad and Hedin's (1982) findings which demonstrate a facilitative influence of service on the development of moral judgment. The research results also are in line with Boss (1994)' study

which indicates that community service is necessary for facilitating moral judgment development. Furthermore, the research findings are in agreement with Hart, Atkins & Donnelly's (2006) belief that community service influences one's moral reasoning and attitudes, development of the self, opportunity for action, personality and social characteristics. According to them, community service participation provides a real-world environment where participants can explore moral questions, engage in moral discourse, perform moral actions and reflect on complicated moral issues.

6 CONCLUSIONS, IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusions

During the process of collecting and analyzing data to answer the research question, results demonstrated that the participants possess good morals and values, but not good ethics. The participants believed that they are not good citizens, lacking basic civic skills and behavior, community service as well as participation in political life and activism. The participants not only believed that extra-curricular activities aiming at their character development in higher education are scarce, but also that university is a place where character development and change happen. Actually, in addition to academic subjects, the university is a place where students learn morals, ethics, values and civic skills thanks to some curricular activities and interaction mainly with their teachers and friends. Last but not least, most respondents reported that they lack extracurricular activities in their universities like clubs, internship programs, vocational training and service learning opportunities.

6.2 Implications and Recommendations

The main objective of this study was to address the correlation between students' extra-curricular experiences and their character in tertiary level. University extracurricular experiences are referred to in this study as participation in extra-curricular activities like volunteering and service learning, vocational trainings, leadership programs, special moral programs and internships programs while character is defined as students' morals, ethics, values and citizenship.

It is essential to note that extra-curricular activities have a positive correlation with students' character and character development. Indeed, the present study is meant to inform students, professors and faculty staff as well as deans and policy makers about the importance of students' college extracurricular activities and the positive relationships such activities have with students' character and character development in the Moroccan high education context. Indeed, the failure to take into consideration, effectively incorporate and benefit from extracurricular activities will squander many opportunities to help students in their character development which positively impacts them and society at large.

The first major practical contribution of the present research is that it provides much needed data on the importance of the university and college environment in the development of students' character. Indeed, Moroccan university deans, administrators and teachers should be

abreast of their important role in developing students' character. They should be aware that they influence students' behavior and that they play a significant role in developing students' ethics and morality although their contact with students is somehow limited. Faculty and university deans and leaders should not only inform the campus community about what is acceptable as moral behavior, but provide education regarding policies, procedures and appropriate actions for developing a strong ethical environment as well. Besides, they should be conscious that a comprehensive college environment that fosters an integrated ethical ethos is one of the best means to enhance character education. Universities should create a positive moral environment and culture by developing a wide range of ethos thanks to leadership, discipline, sense of community, meaningful student government, a moral community, and making time for moral concerns which support and amplify the values taught in classrooms.

The second major contribution of this study is that it provides data on the importance of the approaches and pedagogies in the development of students' character. The Moroccan university has to implement non-traditional approaches to learning such as inquiry-based learning and experiential pedagogies. Moroccan higher education should apply multidimensional approaches so as to teach university students desirable ethics. Furthermore, Moroccan universities should implement pedagogies based on experience because they have much to offer toward this end: exposing students to moral contexts and highlighting inherent ethical concerns. Some of these pedagogies are engaged pedagogies. Moroccan universities should implement *engaged pedagogies*, since they present creative opportunities for students to grow cognitively and form moral habits. Moroccan higher education curricula and programs should be built on prior cognitive and social gains as well as engaged learning and integrated curriculum in order to facilitate students' growth and character development. Part of engaged pedagogies are service learning and community based learning initiatives which should be provided by Moroccan universities for their students. As a matter of fact, Moroccan universities should start *civic classes, projects and other extra-curricular activities* such as community outreach, voluntary service and leadership opportunities because they help students in practicing many values like compassion, cooperation, responsibility and citizenship.

Providing data on the significance of the university special programs in the development of students' character is the third main contribution of this study. Indeed, designing and implementing effective character programs tailored to meet the needs of students, college and society and for the benefits of all of these is a requirement in Moroccan higher education. The aim of these programs is to help students develop the traits and values which translate into moral behavior and action. Effective character education programs should be identified with prevalent practices which include professional development, leadership, mission-driven initiative, social emotional skill training, role models, direct teaching, intrinsic motivation, serving others, nurturing relationships, high expectations and a pedagogy of empowerment. Further, Moroccan universities should implement leadership programs which

help students in the development of social concerns and make them aware of the importance of participating in these activities as well as its positive effects on the gradual transformation in their goals, motives, moral values and beliefs. Last but not least, universities should start honor probation programs which require students to keep a structured journal on both their honor violation and their character development during probation.

Conclusion

This study provides comprehensive data on character education and the correlation between extra-curricular activities and students' morals, ethics, values and citizenship in Moroccan higher education.

Even though this study focuses on students' experiences and attitudes towards extra-curricular activities only, the results would seem to be crucial and beneficial to all internal and external higher education stakeholders in order to improve students' character, moral, ethics and civic engagement and growth in the Moroccan context.

This study has some limitations, though. The first limitation was related to the lack of prior research studies on the topic of character education in tertiary level in Morocco. The researcher was able to find enough literature related to the study in other higher education contexts rather than the Moroccan higher education milieu. The second limitation was the number of sub-variables constituting the main variable of character (morals, ethics, values and citizenship). As a matter of fact, SPSS made it possible to study the targeted correlations. The last limitation was related to the sample size since the number of the participants who filled in the questionnaires was only 220 in addition to 17 participants in the focus groups.

REFERENCES

- Althof & Berkowitz. (2006). Moral education and character education: Their relationship and roles in citizenship education. *Journal of Moral Education*. Vol. 35, No. 4, pp. 495-518. Retrieved from: <https://characterandcitizenship.org/PDF/MoralEducationandCharacterEducationAlthofBerkowitz.pdf>
- Astin, A. W. (1977). *Four critical years*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Astin, A. W. (1993). *What Matters in College? Four Critical Years Revisited*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Batchelder, T. H., & Root, S. (1994). Effects of an undergraduate program to integrate academic learning and service: Cognitive, prosocial cognitive, and identity outcomes. *Journal of Adolescence*, 17, 341-355.
- Battestin, C.; Bergamo, E.; Gazzola, J. (2016). O Filosofar na Dimensão e no Mundo Ético: Confluências com a Educação. *Revista Teias*. 17 (47). Retrieved from: <http://www.periodicos.proped.pro.br/index.php/revistateias/article/view/1906/1468>
- Bock, E. W., Cochran, J. K., & Beeghley, L. (1987). Moral messages: The relative influence of denomination on the religiosity-alcohol relationship. *Sociological Quarterly*, 28: 89-103.
- Boyer, E. L. "Creating the New American College." *Chronicle of Higher Education*, Mar.9, 1994, p. A48.
- Brynildssen, S. (2002). Character education through children's literature. Retrieved from <http://www.ericdigests.org/2003-3/character.html>
- Candee, D. & Kohlberg, L. (1987). Moral judgment and moral action: A reanalysis of Haan, Smith, and Block's (1968) free speech movement data. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 52 (3). pp. 554 – 564.
- Conrad, D., & Hedin, D. (1982). The impact of experiential education on adolescent development. In D. Conrad & D. Hedin, (Eds.), *Child and Youth Services*, special issue Youth participation and experiential education, 4, 57–76.
- Dalton, J. (1985). Promoting values development in college students. *NASPA monograph series*, 4: 3, 63-76.
- Davis, M. (2003). What's wrong with character education? *American Journal of Education*, 110 (November), 32-57.
- De Rusy, C. (2003). Professional ethics begin on the college campus. *The Chronicle of Higher Education*, p. B20.
- Edgington, W. E., Brabham, E. G. & Frost, J.B. (1999). Assessing values in historical fiction written for children: A content analysis of the winners of the Scott O'Dell historical fiction award. *Journal of Children's Literature*, 25(2), 36-49.
- Eyler, J., & Giles, D. E. (1999). *Where's the learning in service-learning?* San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Farhud, Darwich. (2019). Ethics and Society. In *International Journal of Ethics and Society*. Vol. 1, No. 1
- Finney, D.L. (2002). *Character education through student leadership development, citizenship education, and service learning curricula*. Seattle
- Hart, D., Atkins, R., & Ford, D. (1998). Urban America as a context for the development of moral identity in adolescence. *Journal of Social Issues*, 54, 513–530.
- Levine, A. (1980). *When dreams and heroes died*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Levine, A. (1994). "Service on Campus" (editorial). *Change*, 26(4), 4–5.
- Lickona, T. (1993). *Educating for character: How our schools can teach respect and responsibility*. New York: Bantam Books.
- Lickona, T. (2004) *Character Matters: How to help our children develop good judgment, integrity, and other essential virtues*. NY: Golden Rich International.
- Morrill, R. L. (1980). *Teaching values in college*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Sax, L. J., and Astin, A. W. (1997). The benefits of service: Evidence from undergraduates. *Educational Record* 78 (3.4): 25-53.

Sax, L. J. (2004). Citizenship development and the American college student. *New direction for institutional research*, 122, 65-80. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ir.110>

Sindhvani, Anuradha & Kumar, Rajeev. (2013). Values in Higher Education: Need and Importance. Vol. 2, No. 2. pp. 9-14. Retrieved from: <http://www.confabjournals.com/confabjournals/images/632013949362.pdf>

The Council for Industry and Higher Education. (2005). Ethics matters: managing ethical issues in higher education. CIHE and Brunel University. Retrieved from:

<https://www.ibe.org.uk/uploads/assets/02e41a5b-0172-4030-b0d2c9401efe5945/ibecihereportethicsmatters.pdf>

Wardekker, W. (2004). Moral education and the construction of meaning. *Educational Review*, 56 (2), 183 – 192.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Students’ Questionnaires

This questionnaire aims to evaluate students’ character development in higher education and to assess their experiences in university. It consists of two parts: Students character and students' experiences. To measure students’ character development, the questionnaire focuses on three main aspects: morality, ethics, values, and citizenship. Besides, to assess students' college experiences, the questionnaire focuses on curricular activities, extra-curricular activities, and their interactions.

Therefore, you are kindly requested to answer all the items on this questionnaire as sincerely and honestly as possible by choosing the answer that corresponds to your opinion. Your responses are needed to give value to the findings. All the information will be used for research purposes only.

Thank you in advance for your contribution and for the time you will devote to completing this questionnaire.

Part one: Students’ character

Section1: Background information

- 1. What is your age? _____
- 2. Are you?
 Male Female
- 3. What is your educational level?
 First year (undergraduate student)

- Second year (undergraduate student)
- Third year (undergraduate student)
- First year (master student)
- Second year (master student)
- PhD student

4. What are your faculty and university?

5. Did you participate in any of these activities when you were a high schooler?

- Clubs in an association (or an organization)
- Clubs in your high school
- Voluntary work / community service in an association (or organization)
- Voluntary work / community service in your high school

Section 2: Morals

➤ Please circle the answer that best describes your opinion using the following scale:

- 1: Strongly disagree**
- 2: Disagree**
- 3: Agree**
- 4: Strongly agree**

6. I feel that self-esteem is part of my character.	1	2	3	4
7. I feel that I am an honest person.	1	2	3	4
8. I feel that I am a trustworthy person.	1	2	3	4
9. I feel that I am a fair person.	1	2	3	4
10. I feel that I am a respectful person.	1	2	3	4
11. I feel that I am a responsible person.	1	2	3	4
12. I feel that I show compassion to people.)	1	2	3	4
13. I feel that I show an inclination towards humanitarianism	1	2	3	4
14. I feel that I show inclination towards altruism.	1	2	3	4

Section 3: Values

➤ Please circle the answer that best describes your opinion using the following scale:

- 1: Strongly disagree**
- 2: Disagree**

3: Agree

4: Strongly agree

15. I feel that I value kindness (being kind to the self and other).	1	2	3	4
16. I feel that I value justice .	1	2	3	4
17. I feel that I value love , loving the good and doing the good to myself and to others.	1	2	3	4
18. I feel that I value wisdom .	1	2	3	4
19. I feel that I value hard work .	1	2	3	4
20. I feel that I value gratitude .	1	2	3	4
21. I feel that value humility .	1	2	3	4
22. I feel that I hold positive attitudes more than ever.	1	2	3	4
23. I feel that I am a courteous person.	1	2	3	4

Section 4: Ethics

➤ Please circle the answer that best describes your opinion using the following scale:

1: Strongly disagree

2: Disagree

3: Agree

4: Strongly agree

24. I feel that I am a generous person.	1	2	3	4
25. I think that showing empathy towards others is important to me.	1	2	3	4
26. I feel that dishonesty , for example academic dishonesty and cheating , is a derogatory virtue.	1	2	3	4
27. I feel that perseverance is important to me.	1	2	3	4
28. I feel that I am a self-disciplined person.	1	2	3	4
29. I feel that I am a courageous person.	1	2	3	4
30. I feel that dedication is important to me.	1	2	3	4
31. I feel that I am willing to accept criticism .	1	2	3	4
32. I feel that I am willing to learn from failure .	1	2	3	4

Section 5: Citizenship

➤ Please circle the answer that best describes your opinion using the following scale:

1: Strongly disagree

2: Disagree

3: Agree

4: Strongly agree

33. I feel that participating in political life is important to me.	1	2	3	4
34. I feel that participating in civic life is important to me.	1	2	3	4
35. I feel that having civic skills .	1	2	3	4
36. I feel that I am interested in addressing community (society) problems .	1	2	3	4
37. I feel that I am confident in my ability to be an effective force of change .	1	2	3	4
38. I feel that I am interested in community service .	1	2	3	4
39. I feel that I am interested in voluntary work .	1	2	3	4
40. I feel that I am interested in political activism .	1	2	3	4
41. I feel that I am interested in social movement activism in college.	1	2	3	4
42. I feel that I am a socially responsible citizen .	1	2	3	4
43. I feel that working for the common good in my society is important to me.	1	2	3	4

Part II: Students' College Experiences

This part aims to collect data on students' experiences in the university. It focuses on three main aspects: curricular activities, extra-curricular activities and students' interactions. Therefore, you are kindly requested to answer all the items by choosing the best answer that describes your opinion.

Section 1: Curricular Activities

➤ Please choose the answer that best describes your opinion using the following scale:

1: Never

2: Rarely

3: Sometimes

4: Often

5: Always

44. I feel myself engaged in the classroom activities.	1	2	3	4	5
45. My learning is inquiry-based learning . It is active learning that usually starts with questions as well as real life problems and scenarios.	1	2	3	4	5
46. My learning is problem solving based through which I am actively engaged while the teacher is a facilitator.	1	2	3	4	5
47. My learning in class is experiential learning in that I learn through experience and reflection on what I do in class.	1	2	3	4	5
48. I am required to conduct research or make presentations about character (morals, ethics, values or citizenship).	1	2	3	4	5
49. I am encouraged to discuss moral dilemmas with my classmates and teachers in the classroom.	1	2	3	4	5
50. I am involved in decision making within the classroom.	1	2	3	4	5
51. I participate in classroom activities requiring opinion conflict resolution about moral issues and dilemma.	1	2	3	4	5
52. I learn in a warm and supportive classroom environment where students feel free to express their thoughts and feelings and to be tolerant of different student opinions.	1	2	3	4	5
53. I participate in open classroom	1	2	3	4	5

discussions about challenging moral issues and ethical discussions.					
---	--	--	--	--	--

Section 2: Extra-curricular Activities

➤ Please circle the answer that best describes your opinion using the following scale:

- 1: Never**
- 2: Rarely**
- 3: Sometimes**
- 4: Often**
- 5: Always**

54. I participate in extra-curricular activities like civic classes, projects, conferences, lecture series and department colloquia aiming at developing students' character in my university.	1	2	3	4	5
55. I participate in leadership programs in my college.	1	2	3	4	5
56. I participate in volunteering and service learning opportunities in my college.	1	2	3	4	5
57. I participate in college special programs to foster students' moral development in my college.	1	2	3	4	5
58. I participate in college internships programs to develop my expertise in areas of civic interest.	1	2	3	4	5
59. I participate in vocational trainings and programs provided by my college.	1	2	3	4	5
60. I participate in my college clubs such as athleticism, cinema, theater, media, tutoring, music, news, career and the like.	1	2	3	4	5
61. I participate and assist in the development of the university codes of conduct and ethics with other students, teachers and administration staff.	1	2	3	4	5
62. I meet and talk to faculty staff and professionals about issues related to academic dishonesty and honesty like cheating and plagiarism.	1	2	3	4	5
63. I meet Student Affairs Professionals who provide services and support for student success at institutions of higher education to enhance student	1	2	3	4	5

Section 3: Students' Interactions

➤ P
l
e
a
s
e
c
i
r
c
l
e
t
h
e
a
n
s
w
e
r

t
h
a
t

b
e
s
t

d

describes your opinion using the following scale:

- 1: Never**
- 2: Rarely**
- 3: Sometimes**
- 4: Often**
- 5: Always**

64. I create and maintain interpersonal relationships with new people.	1	2	3	4	5
65. I create and maintain close relationships with family members and friends.	1	2	3	4	5
66. I seek the company of serious students who are role models and display good character.	1	2	3	4	5
67. I hold and maintain caring relationships with my teachers, classmates and faculty administrators and personnel.	1	2	3	4	5
68. I interact with my teachers individually if I need to.	1	2	3	4	5
69. I interact effectively with my classmates although we may have different values and points of view.	1	2	3	4	5
70. I interact effectively with my teachers although we may have different values and points of view.	1	2	3	4	5
71. I interact effectively with faculty administrators although we may have different values and points of view.	1	2	3	4	5

72. If you have any comments, remarks or suggestions, please feel free to mention them below.

.....

Thank you very much for your help!

Appendix 2: The Focus Group

This focus group aims to evaluate students' character development in higher education and to assess their experiences in university as well as the relation between them. To measure students' character development, this group interview focuses on four main aspects: morals, ethics, values, and citizenship. Besides, to assess students'

college experiences, the focus group focuses on curricular activities, extra-curricular activities, and their interactions.

The participants will remain anonymous and all the information will be used for research purposes only.

Thank you in advance for your contribution and for the time you will devote to participating in this focus group.

Opening Questions

➤ What are your names? Age? Hobbies?

Key Questions

☞ What is your opinion about students' participation in clubs or community service in high schools or associations when they were high schoolers?

A. Students' Character

1. What is your opinion on university students' character? (morals, values, ethics)

Morality

What is your opinion on university students' morals? (self-esteem, honest, trustworthy, fair, respectful, responsible, compassionate, humane, altruistic)

Values

2. What is your opinion on university students' values? (kindness, justice, love, wisdom, hard work, gratitude, humility, positive attitudes and courtesy).

II. Ethics

3. What is your opinion on university students' ethics? (generosity, empathy, perseverance, self-discipline, courtesy, courage, accepting criticism and willing to learn from failure)

III. Citizenship

4. What do you feel about university students' citizenship?
5. What is your opinion about the impact of the university on students' character?

A. Student's College Experiences:

I. Curricular activities

6. What do you think about the university curriculum of English?
7. What do you think about the impact of the university curriculum of English on students' character?

II. Extra-curricular activities

8. What do you think about the university extra-curricular activities?

9. What do you think about the impact of the university extracurricular activities on students' character?

III. Students' interactions

10. What do you think about Students' interactions (interacting with their friends, classmates, teachers, faculty staff and university personnel) Interacting effectively with my teachers although we may have different values and points of view.

11. What do you think about the impact of students' interactions in the university on their character? (interacting with their friends, classmates, teachers, faculty staff and university personnel)

Ending Questions:

(After summarizing the group interview discussion)

- Did we forget something? Is there anything else you would like to say or to add?
- Thank you so much for your time, cooperation and patience.